

ILLICIT DRUG TRAFFICKING: A SOUTH AFRICAN REPORT ON THE EXTENT OF THE GLOBAL TRADING

Shaka Yesufu

Department of Research and Development, University of Limpopo, Turfloop, Sovenga, Limpopo Republic of South Africa
E-mail: Shakazulu17@yahoo.co.uk
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8002-3074>

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received date 05.05.2022

Accepted date 23.06.2022

Published date 30.06.2022

Section:

Communication Studies

DOI

10.21303/2313-8416.2022.002552

KEY WORDS

drugs trafficking
narcotics
illicit
organized crime
global
crime
police
syndicate
mafia
drug lords

ABSTRACT

The objects of this research are: first, to explore some of the issues relating to drug trafficking in South Africa. Second, to highlight the devastating consequences of drug abuse on citizens, our brothers, and sisters whose lives have been destroyed and cut short. Third, to explore, government policies, police efforts, and citizens to combat the social menace of illicit drug trafficking plaguing us.

The researcher investigated the following problems: drug trafficking and its impact on individuals or citizens and society, barriers faced by law enforcement to stop the illicit borderless organized crime.

The main results of the research are: first, drug trafficking is a lucrative global phenomenon that is very difficult to stop over the years. Second, is the identification of varieties of drugs found in South African markets, their origins, transit, and final destinations. Third, reporting the extent of drug seizures in South Africa explains why the trade has continued unabated over the years. Fourth, highlights the need for a collective and suggestive way to consign drug trafficking to history.

The area of practical use of the research is for all citizens, law enforcement officers affected by the illicit trade, communities, countries, research students, social workers, and staff members of social welfare and criminal justice departments.

© The Author(s) 2021. This is an open access article under the Creative Commons CC BY license

1. Introduction

Drug trafficking the global illicit trade involving the cultivation, manufacture, distribution, and sale of controlled substances is estimated to be around \$32 billion in the industry [1]. Drug trafficking financial flows have global dimensions linking regions and continents, destroying the lives of the consumers irrespective of their nationalities, sex, race, class, or status in society. Drug trafficking is a monstrous evil plaguing humanity for centuries with no end in sight to the malaise and menace caused by it. A drug can be defined as a natural or synthetic substance that is used to produce physiological or psychological effects in humans or other higher-order animals. Drugs may mean something different to individuals depending on their availability and purpose. To some, drugs are a necessity for sustaining and prolonging life, to others, drugs provide an escape from the pressures and demands of life or a means of ending it [2]. Various factors can be held responsible for the increase in drug abuse in South Africa as follows: Influx of migrants, porous border, corrupt officials at the border posts, high unemployment rates, weakened family social structures, establishment of clandestine drug-making laboratories, urbanization, and the quest to Westernization by new city dwellers.

South Africa's geographical location and its international trade links with countries in Asia, Latin America, Western Europe, and North America have made it an attractive drug transit country. South Africa has an excellent infrastructure of roads and rail, telecommunication, airports, and seaports facilities. All of these are also used to transit illicit drugs, particularly, cocaine, heroin, and methaqualone [3]. With the end of the apartheid regime, South Africa opened its borders to migrants coming from other African countries, Europe, Latin America, and the rest of the world heralding the dawn of our new democratic dispensation of governance. Big cities like Johannesburg, Cape Town, and Durban become highly populated as both internal and international migration to these big cities for economic pursuits increased post-1994. In overpopulated cities, one is bound to deal with high levels of crime, and acute shortages of housing, schools, jobs, and hospitals. In most cases, drug use is subject to class and affordability. The rich and affluent can afford cocaine, the

working class are able to afford cannabis, the middle class is able to afford LSD and Heroin, and the underclass those and constituents who occupy the lower strata of society are able to afford cannabis and Nyaope, and in some instances glue sniffing. Basically, drug use and its addiction are based on affordability, a pay-as-you-go process.

1. 1. Objects of the research

The objects of the research are to explore the extent of illicit drug trafficking within the South African context. To find strategies to combat it.

1. 2. Problem descriptions of drug trafficking

Drug trafficking is a serious problem in South Africa. The researcher explores a few of the landmark drug seizures leading to arrests of drug dealers. These incidents highlight the fact that South Africa is faced with drug trafficking social problems. Young school pupils are experimenting with drugs and teachers in some instances are too scared to reprimand them. Our streets are no longer safe due to high numbers of robberies and the level of violence deployed by their attackers is cause for serious concern. The issue of youth’s high unemployment rate has also exacerbated the drug dependency culture. The social gap has got widened over the years and South Africa is seen as one of the most unequal countries in the world.

SAPS Drug statistic report.

To put drug-related crime in South Africa into context, the researcher drew a comparison from the South African Police crime statistics for October to December 2020–2021. The top five police stations where drug-related crimes were reported are in the Western Cape provinces as follows (Table 1).

Table 1

The South African Police Service Crime Statistics Report OCT-DEC 2020–2021

Police Station	Province	October to December 2020–2021	% Change October to December 2021–2022	Count Diff	% Change
Kraaifontein	Western Cape	389	756	367	94.3 %
Lentegeur	Western Cape	396	724	328	82.8 %
Knysna	Western Cape	66	238	172	260.6 %
Durbanville	Western Cape	100	222	122	122.0 %
Harare	Western Cape	122	204	87	67.2 %

Source: South African Police Service crime stats report 2021/2022 [4]

One can deduce from the above table that all five police stations indicated that the Western Cape has a major problem with drugs. The researcher argues that some of the areas highlighted need more proactive, and intelligence-led policing put in place. Next, the researcher investigates the research problems of the study.

Types of drugs found in South Africa.

Cannabis.

Cannabis is the widest most found drug in South Africa. The use of cannabis also known as *dagga* in South Africa dates to the 15th century. Arab, as well as Persian and Indian merchants, were responsible for its spread along the eastern coast of the African continent (13th century). In 1928, authorities in South Africa introduced the first legislation concerning cannabis [5]. The use of cannabis initially was restricted largely to the African population. But within the last decade, we have seen a shift to include the colored and white populace [3]. Cannabis sativa belongs to the world drug list of Hallucinogens. This is a substance that includes changes in mood, attitude, thought processes, and perceptions. Cannabis preparation normally consists of crushed leaves mixed in varying proportions with the plant’s flower, stem, and seed. The plant secretes a sticky resin known as hashish. The resinous material can also be extracted from the plant by soaking in a solvent such as alcohol. The Cannabis plant contains a chemical known as *tetrahydrocannabinol (THC)*, which produces the psychoactive effects experienced by its users. The potency and resulting effects of the drug fluctuate, depending on the relative proportion of the plant consumed. The most common method of administration is by smoking either the dried flowers and leaves or various preparations

of it. Cannabis can also be taken orally, typically baked in sweets such as brownies or cookies [2]. At the lower usage, the user may experience an increase in sense of well-being; initial restlessness and hilarity followed by a dreamy, carefree state of relaxation; alteration of sensory perceptions including expansion of space and time; a more vivid sight, smell, taste and sound; a feeling of hunger, especially a craving for sweets; and subtle changes in thought formation and expression [6]. At a higher usage, there are changes in the user causing psychotomimetic phenomena which include: distortion of body image, loss of personal identity, sensory and mental illusions, fantasies, and hallucinations [7].

Lysergic Acid Diethylamide (LSD). This drug is also a part of the Hallucinogen group. LSD is a substance derived from ergot, which is a type of fungus that attacks certain grasses and grains. Its hallucinogenic effects were first described by Swiss chemist Albert Hofman after he accidentally ingested some of the material in his laboratory in 1943. The drug is a very potent one, 25 micrograms are enough to start vivid visual hallucinations that can last for about 12 hours. LSD is mostly imported from Europe into South Africa; it has emerged as a drug of choice among several groups of mostly white Africans over the last few decades [8]. LSD is called several names in South Africa: candy, microdots, trips, tab, and hofmanns. It is a colourless and odourless substance with psychedelic compositions. The side effects include a predisposition to psychosis, exacerbation of depression, and other mental illnesses. The use of LSD seems to be common in rave clubs for 18–23 years old in Gauteng, Cape Town, and Port Elizabeth [9].

Mandrax (Methaqualone). This is the second most widely abused substance in South Africa. It started to become a problem in South African Society in the late 1980s. Mandrax has been widespread amongst the Indian and coloured Communities. In the early 90s, it started to spread among the black community as well. It is mainly imported from abroad about 80 % and 20 % from local production factories. The first Mandrax clandestine laboratory was discovered in 1987 [10]. Some factories were also discovered in the East Rand and Western Cape region [11]. Mandrax is mainly trafficked into South Africa from India, via Dubai, or via routes in Zaire and other African countries [12].

Cocaine. Between 1884 and 1887, Sigmund Freud described his experiments with cocaine as a source of “exhilaration and lasting euphoria” that permitted “intensive mental or physical work to be performed without fatigue...It is as though the need for food and sleep was completely banished” [13]. Cocaine can be used as a pain killer and anaesthetic. It is a powerful stimulant to the central nervous system, and its effects are increased alertness, and vigor, suppression of hunger, fatigue, and boredom. Cocaine is commonly sniffed or snorted and is absorbed into the body through the mucous membranes of the nose [2]. In the past, South Africa only served as a transshipment place for cocaine from Latin America to Europe and more recently Australia. Some cocaine was brought into South Africa by West Africans notably Nigerians who settled around the Johannesburg area. In recent years, South Africa is increasingly becoming an important market for cocaine [10].

Crack Cocaine. Crack cocaine is found in South Africa. It is a particularly potent form of cocaine. It is a product derived from mixing cocaine with baking soda and water and then heating the resulting solution. This material is then dried and broken into tiny chunks that dealers sell as crack “rocks” that are volatile to be smoked. The faster the cocaine level rises in the brain, the greater the euphoria, and the quickest way to obtain a rise in the brain cocaine level is to smoke crack [14].

Heroin. Heroin is a central nervous system (CNS) depressant that relieves pain and induces sleep. Most heroin originates from the opium poppy farms in Southeast Asia (Myanmar, Colombia). The opium is converted to morphine in labs near the fields and then to heroin in labs within or near the producing country. After importation, drug dealers cut, or dilute the heroin before selling it to addicts [15].

Alcohol. Many people overlooked the fact that alcohol is a form of drug that falls into the classification of (barbiturates) or depressants. A depressant is a substance that depresses the function of the central nervous system, depressants calm irritability and anxiety and may induce sleep. The behavioural patterns of alcohol vary and depend on the individual, social setting, and the amount of consumption. Some people drink alcohol and become more talkative, in contrast, some drinkers may become quieter and withdraw, and other kinds of drinkers may become emotionally

attached seeking attention. Worst drinkers may become very aggressive and want to pick a fight with everybody they come across. When alcohol enters the bloodstream, it quickly travels to the brain, where it suppresses the brain's control of thought and processes. Low doses of alcohol tend to inhibit the mental processes of judgment, memory, and concentration. The drinker's personality becomes expansive, he or she exudes confidence. When taken in moderate doses, alcohol reduces coordination substantially, inhibits orderly thoughts and processes and speech patterns, and slows reaction times. Under these circumstances, the ability to walk or drive become noticeably impaired. Higher doses of alcohol may cause the user to become highly irritable and emotional, displays of anger and crying are not uncommon. Extremely high doses may cause an individual to lapse into unconsciousness or even a comatose state that may precede a fatal depression of circulatory and respiratory functions [16].

The extent of alcohol consumption was brought to scrutiny during Covid 19 shutdown by the government in March 2020, and the sale of all intoxicating liquor was banned. Alcohol users struggled to cope with the realities of staying free from it. It was reported that off licenses liquor shops were broken into and in some instances, members of the South African police service were working clandestinely to ensure that the sale of alcohol was sold illegally to members of the public. Police officers were arrested for transporting alcohol during this period. There was a huge cry that the ban on alcohol be lifted as some citizens were struggling to cope with life without alcohol, and court challenges were launched against the government to lift the ban on alcohol. For the first time, South Africa came to grasp the level of alcohol drinkers' culture that permeates society. It shows how alcohol has become part of some of us a sine qua non that we cannot live without. Even during the partial lockdown, at supermarkets, the researcher observed that the queues for customers waiting to serve alcohol were far much longer than that of customers purchasing food. This was an eye opener for some of us who have previously underestimated the level of alcohol as part of our social existence in South Africa [17].

Amphetamines. This is another kind of stimulant drug found in South Africa. A stimulant is a substance taken to increase alertness or speed up the central nervous system. Amphetamines are a group of synthetic drugs referred to as "uppers". Administering a therapeutic dose of 5–20 milligrams per day, taken orally, provides a feeling of well-being and increased alertness that is followed by a decrease in fatigue and a loss of appetite, this is then followed by a period of restlessness and instability or apprehension, and once the stimulant effect wears off, depression may set in. Users have reported experiencing a euphoria that produces hyperactivity with a feeling of clarity of vision as well as hallucinations. As the effect of the amphetamines wears off, the individual lapses into a period of exhaustion and may sleep continuously for one or two days [2]. Following this, the user often experiences a prolonged period of severe depression lasting from days to weeks. A type of amphetamine called "Ice" emerged on the market a few years ago. Ice is a smokable type of drug and its effects last longer. Chronic users may exhibit violent destructive behaviour and acute psychosis similar to paranoid schizophrenia. Repeated use of amphetamines leads to a stronger psychological dependency, which encourages their continued administration

Nyaope. A new addictive drug "nyaope" commonly known as "Whoonga" is used by black South African and found mainly in townships and black residential areas. Nyaope is a mixture of low-grade heroin, cannabis products, antiretroviral drugs, and other materials added as bulking agents [18]. Nyaope is a cocktail drug commonly used in the Tshwane townships, it is very addictive and difficult to quit. The resultant difficulties include financial, social, and mental, specifically depression and anxiety [19]. The recognised symptoms for Nyaope users include the following [20]:

- hyperactivity;
- been secretive and suspicious;
- change in sleeping pattern;
- developing a low appetite for food;
- sudden weight loss;
- body odor;
- change in the colour of eyes.

Anabolic Steroids. Anabolic steroids are synthetic compounds that are chemically related to the male sex hormone testosterone which promotes muscle growth. Testosterone has two different effects on the body. It promotes the development of secondary male characteristics (androgen

effects), and it accelerates muscle growth (anabolic effect). Anabolic steroids can be classified into three headings namely:

- bulking steroids for building muscles;
- performance steroids for strength and endurance;
- cutting steroids for burning fat [21].

Long-term use side effects include heart problems, liver cancer and malfunctions, diminished sex drives in males, and infertility in women users [22].

1. 3. Suggested solutions to drug trafficking

In this part of the research, the researcher looks at some initiatives taken by the South government to control the influx of illicit drugs in and out of the country.

1. 3. 1. The Drug Master Plan (NDMP)

The National Drug Master Plan (NDMP) 2013–2017 of South Africa was formulated by the Central Drug Authority (CDA) in terms of the Prevention and treatment of drug dependence Act (20 of 1992), as amended, as well as the Prevention of and Treatment for Substance Abuse Act (70 of 2008). The National Drug Master Plan offers a balanced approach to collaboration on drug control and should help South Africa fight the scourge of substance abuse and set the country firmly on the road to creating a healthy nation. It states in its opening forward message by the Minister of social development Ms B Dlamini that: “The impact of alcohol and substance abuse continues to ravage families, communities, and society. The youths of South Africa are particularly hard hit due to increases in the harmful use of alcohol and the use and abuse of illicit drugs... Alcohol and drugs damage the health of their users and are linked to rises in non-communicable diseases including HIV and AIDS, cancer, heart disease, and psychological disorders. Users are also exposed to violent crimes either as perpetrators or victims of and are also at risk of long-term unemployment due to school dropout and foetal alcohol syndrome, being with conflict with the law and loss of employment. Costs of rehabilitation, ostracized from families, and involved in road accidents death. The plan is intended to help raise the vision of a society free of substance abuse, the delivery of evidence-based strategy to meet the needs of communities”. The NDMP has the following overall objectives:

- ensure coordination of efforts to reduce the demand, supply, and harm caused by substances of abuse;
- ensure effective and efficient services for combating substances of abuse through the elimination of drug trafficking and related crimes;
- strengthen mechanisms for implementing cost-effective interventions to empower vulnerable groups;
- ensure the sharing of current good practices in reducing harm including social ills related-substance abuse;
- provide a framework for the commissioning of relevant research;
- provide a framework for Monitoring and Evaluation;
- promote national, regional, and international cooperation to reduce the supply of drugs and other substances of abuse [23].

1. 3. 2. Legislations

The researcher explores some legislations enacted by the South African government to control drug trafficking as follows.

1. The Drugs and Drugs Trafficking Act 140 of 1992 aims to provide the following:

- a) for the prohibition of the use or possession of, or the dealing in, drugs and of certain acts relating to the manufacture or supply of certain substances or the acquisition or conversion of the proceeds of certain crimes;
- b) for the obligation to report certain information to the police;
- c) for the exercise of the powers of entry, search, and seizure, and detention in specified circumstances;
- d) for the recovery of the proceeds of drug trafficking;
- e) for matters connected therewith [24].

2. The Prevention of, and Treatment for Substance Abuse Act 2008, is supported by the Drug Master Plan 2013–17, which sets out the strategies and measures to be used to combat substance abuse. Interventions proposed in the Plan are based on the supply and demand framework, i.e., reducing demand, harm, and supply, establishment and registration of programmes and services, including prevention, early intervention, treatment and reintegration, and after-care; and facilitating collaboration among government departments and other stakeholders; establishment of the Central Drug Authority (CDA) to monitor and oversee activities of the CDA.

3. The National Liquor Act, 2003 the primary focus is on the regulation of the liquor industry. The Act seeks to facilitate alcohol abuse and promote the development of a responsible and sustainable liquor industry and provides for public participation in liquor licensing issues. Provincial Liquor Bills/Acts Provision of liquor licenses for the retail sale of alcohol; establishment of Liquor Boards; establishment of liquor officers and inspectors; and provide for the appointment of municipalities as agents of the Liquor Board and liquor licensing authorities [25].

4. Education Laws amendment Act, 2007 Provides for a random search, seizure, and drug testing at schools [26].

5. National Road Traffic Act, 1996) Deals with matters related to drinking and drug use while driving; breath tests, blood tests and recognition of signs of drug use/ intoxication; testing/enforcement equipment; transportation of drugs; legal blood alcohol limit [27].

1. 3. 3. International treaties and agreements

South Africa is a signatory to the United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances 1971. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime has some presence in South Africa through the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime Southern Africa office. Its drug-related mandate includes strengthening the legislative and judicial capacity to ratify and implement international conventions and instruments on drug control, organized crime, corruption, terrorism, and money-laundering; reducing drug trafficking, and enhancing the capacity of government institutions and civil society organizations to prevent drug use and the spread of related infections. South Africa is also signatories to the following:

- The 1961 Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs.
- The 1972 Protocol amending the 1961 Single Convention.
- South Africa is a signatory to the Southern Community Development Community (SADC)

Protocol on combating illicit drugs with the following objectives:

1. To reduce and eventually eliminate drug trafficking, money laundering, corruption, and the illicit use and abuse of drugs through cooperation among enforcement agencies and demand reduction through coordinated programmes in the Region.
2. To eliminate the production of illicit drugs, and
3. To protect the region from being used as a conduit for drugs destined for international markets.

1. 3. 4. South African National Council on Alcoholism and Drug Dependence (SANCA)

SANCA strives to address substance abuse and various addictions through the provision of specialised education, treatment, prevention, and aftercare services to all people, thereby enhancing the quality of life and helping to restore their self-respect and dignity. SANCA has developed a standardised treatment programmes consistent with the latest research and according to International and National treatment principles and standards. SANCA also offers treatment on a continuum of care from screening, assessment, medical treatment, and therapeutic treatment for service users and families as well as aftercare services. According to a recent report published by SANCA

“The prohibition of the sale of alcohol during levels 3 to 5 of the lockdown during the Covid-19 Pandemic further reinforced that South Africans have a problematic relationship with alcohol use. The desperation was seen in the making of homebrew concoctions, illegal trade in alcohol, and robberies of liquor stores. Families that were now isolated could now experience the impact of addiction. The lifting of the prohibition on alcohol sales during level 3 of lockdown further raised concerns about the increase in crime and gender-based violence” [28].

2. Materials and methods

The researcher consulted existing literature on drug trafficking, gathering secondary data as the basis knowledge informing the research. Previous works related to the research topic were read and grouped into relevant headings as it relates to the topic.

The author conducted an extensive review of Literature relying on the following secondary data sources as follows:

- The United Nations Office for Drugs Control and Crime Prevention (UNODC) Reports.
- The South African Police Service (SAPS) Annual Crime Statistical Reports.
- The South African Revenue Service (SARS) Annual Reports.
- The South African Medical Research Council (SAMR) Reports.
- The Republic of South Africa Government Drug Master Plan 2013–2017.
- The Institute for Security Studies (ISS) South Africa Published Periodic Monographs.
- South Africa’s Drug related legislations (the Drugs and drugs Trafficking Act 140 of 1992; National Liquor Act, 2003; Education Laws Amendment Act, 2007; National Road Traffic Act, 1996; Education law amendment Act, 2007 and the National Road Traffic Act, 1996.

3. Results and discussions

The research reports the following drug seizure incidents as follows:

1. On 17 May 2021, it was reported in the South African Broadcasting Corporation news channel that “Cannabis, Cocaine seized in Niger and South Africa during drug bust operation” 973 cocaine bricks worth over R550 Million (\$ 50 million USD) were seized from a ferry vessel [29].

2. On Tuesday, April 19, 2011, it was reported in the South African Government news that “Police seize drugs and equipment worth billions” It was one of the largest drug-related seizures for many years in Kraaifontein Western Cape [30].

3. On February 4, 2022, it was reported in the South African Government news that “SARS seize drugs worth R21 million (\$1.5m USD) at Oliver Tambo International Airport Johannesburg” drugs hidden inside vehicle catalytic converters en route to Dubai and Jordan [30].

4. On 21 June 2021, it was reported by SABC news that “Police hunt for one Mr Ahmed Isa in connection with drugs worth R400million (\$40million USD). Mr Isa is also wanted by Interpol on a RED alert notice in Belgium for previous outstanding drug and money laundering charges. The Hawks (South Africa Narcotics Enforcement Bureau) have publicly declared Mr Isa wanted his involvement in a drug syndicate transportation of drugs worth R400 million on the N1 motorway in Pretoria in June 2021. Mr Isa was last seen at Camps Bay Cape Town when he evaded arrest from the police. Members of the public have been warned not to approach Mr Isa directly as he is known to be armed and violent. They are advised to immediately report any sight of him to the police. As the hunt for him continues [31].

5. On 8 August 2021, it was reported by Cheryl Kahlia that “Cocaine worth R720 million (72 million USD) was confiscated at Port Elizabeth, Eastern Cape Province. With the assistance of Interpol, a shipping vessel from Brazil en route to India and Singapore with cargo was intercepted with 3, 369 pack bags of cocaine [31].

6. South African tries to ship R1.4b worth of drugs to Australia. According to “Business Insider”, Australian border police arrested two men in New South Wales in July 2019, seizing 384 kilograms of cocaine in the biggest ever single drug bust in the history of its federal police force. The stash represents almost half as much as the total of all cocaine detected at Australian borders in 2018. Police put the street value of the find at the equivalent of R1.4b. The drugs were found welded into a giant; yellow Cat excavator shipped from South Africa [32].

In looking at the value of the seized drugs above, one can safely argue that South Africa is having very serious drug trafficking problems. Drug syndicates are determined to flood South Africa with the supply of illicit drugs. Law enforcement officers have a huge task ahead of them as the seizures tell a vivid story of a country at war with drug dealers. Are they winning the war?

Drug control strategies.

The researcher argues that the South African government must put in place very robust, proactive short and long-term strategies to combat drug trafficking. Drug trafficking is carried out by drug kingpins with elements of planning and sophistication. The use of technology has become

a double-edged used by international drug dealers and law enforcement agencies. The researcher calls for the use of drones to keep surveillance on all territorial borders of South Africa.

Open and relax borders.

According to the researchers, South Africa has a porous border control, and this makes it more attractive to international drug syndicates to enter and leave with minimal control put in place. South Africa is easily accessible by air, sea, road, and waterways [33]. Cartographers describe South Africa as a country with approximately 3500 kilometers of continuous border with other southern African states. The entire territorial space is described as extremely porous, with fifty-two possible legal and illegal entry points and with border walls not fit for purpose erected [34]. A further border lapse has been identified in South African airports where the illegal system of ‘shotgunning’ has been adopted by drug traffickers to evade detection. A shotgunning technique is a modus operandi commonly used by a drug syndicate that sponsors multiple couriers on the same flight to almost guarantee that, at least some of the drug mules will eventually slip the customs checkpoint undetected in a confusion created by multiple detections[35].

The researcher argues that if South Africa is going to take the fight against drug trafficking more seriously, it must first tackle the issue of its porous borders making it difficult for organised criminals to make South Africa becoming a haven for them to ply their trade. The whole issue of immigration and border posts must be addressed as a matter of urgency. There is a relatively contested ongoing debate about any country that gets immigration control of their border right, crime will be reduced. The researcher concurs with this line of argument and avers that every constitutionally elected government has a duty to protect its citizens from all forms of crime within and outside its borders. One can also allude to the fact that a social contract does exist between citizens and democratic governments.

Anti-corruption.

The image of the South African Police Service (SAPS) has been severely damaged due to the reporting of rampant and reckless corruption among its rank and file. The author argues that if nothing is done to address the level of institutionalised corruption, our democracy may suffer as a consequence [34]. Collusion between police members and drug syndicates has been recorded in South Africa. In some cases, police officials are asked by syndicates or drug dealers to use policing powers to undermine competition from other syndicates. In countries where corruption is rampant, it is extremely difficult to plan countermeasures without them being compromised at an early stage due to the involvement of political officials [33].

Recommendations:

1. Life in imprisonment for anyone who imports or exports illicit drugs from South Africa.
2. Assets forfeiture for all drug dealers.
3. Swift extradition.
4. Effective judiciary.
5. Well-resourced police service.
6. Dismissal of any police officers linked to the drugs trade.
7. Schools’ curricula to dedicate more time to studying the harmful effects of drugs.
8. Stricter border controls in air, sea, and land entry and existing posts of the country.
9. Confiscation of the vessels, planes, cars, and any means of transportation of the drugs.
10. Failure to report a drug dealer should become a crime.
11. Educating members of the public about the impact of drugs on individuals and society.
12. Parents, traditional, community, and religious leaders must be proactive and become appointed drug czars assigned responsibilities.
13. Government must declare zero tolerance to drug trafficking and users in its yearly policies and implement them.
14. Increased budget for rehabilitation centers.

Limitations of the study.

This study has some limitations due to the high risk associated with conducting the sensitive nature of the topic relating to drugs trafficking. Drugs dealers and associates sees the researcher as a possible threat to their means of livelihood. The researcher acknowledges the high level of risks associated with the study. The researcher opined that there is room for further research related to

the topic under study. More emphasis should be paid to the following key areas as a basis for future research as follows:

- conducting qualitative interviews with convicted drug dealers in prison;
- interviews with relatives of drug addicts to measure the impact of drugs on family;
- explore the lifestyles and social status of drug dealers in our communities;
- identifying the link (s) between a drug dealer and drug user.

4. Conclusion

Drug trafficking and its use is destroying the lives of people, men, and women, young and old, black, white, colored, and Indian are all faced with the scourge of illicit drugs. South Africa remains a supplier of narcotics, a recipient of it, and acts as a conduit route for the supply and transportation of illicit drugs globally. The researcher draws the conclusion that first, society must join their hands together to find a long-term solution to drug trafficking. The war against drugs cannot be fought and won by the police alone, drugs trafficking is a global business that needs local, national, and international efforts to combat it. Second, citizens must make a civic duty to report drug dealers in our communities regardless of their status in society. Drugs are very harmful, when hooked on them, it becomes very difficult to stop the craving for them, rehabilitation does not guarantee a break free from it. Drug dealers are known to be very violent people, they must be reported to the police. Society must adopt a zero tolerance toward drug dealers making our communities less accommodative for dealers, drug lords, and drug barons who feed on the predicament of the addicted. Say NO to drugs.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Acknowledgment

First, I thank the almighty God for the gift of wisdom, knowledge, and intelligence bestowed upon us. It is my sacred belief that by using the pen, we can reconstruct societal ills confronting us. I dedicate this article to all peoples of the world who are suffering from drug abuse, be it relatives, or friends you may know hoping that they beat their addiction wherever they may be. Illicit drugs are harmful, I salute the men and women in uniform who are fighting crime 24/7 to keep our country's security border post safe from drug dealers. This article would not have been written without the support of my dear wife Mrs Melbourne Kweyama- Yesufu and our three lovely children: Earl Yesufu, Chelsy Yesufu and Brooklyn Yesufu. Together WE SAY NO TO DRUGS.

References

- [1] United Nations. Available at: www.unodc.org
- [2] Saferstein, R. (2015). *Criminalistics: An Introduction to Forensic Science*. Harlow: Pearson Global, 552.
- [3] South Africa Country Profile on Drugs and Crime (1999). United Nations Office for Drugs Control and Crime Prevention. Available at: https://www.unodc.org/documents/southafrica/sa_drug.pdf
- [4] South African Police Service crime stats report 2021/2022. Available at: <https://www.saps.gov.za/services/crimestats.php>
- [5] Wright, J. W. (1991). *The Drugs Situation in South Africa- drug Trafficking in South Africa and Trends in the Southern Sub-Region of Africa*. Drugs Arena.
- [6] *Marijuana- A Signal of Misunderstanding* (1972). Washington: US Government. Printing Office.
- [7] Smith, F., Siegel, J. A. (Eds.) (2005). *Handbook of Forensic Drug Analysis*. Boca Raton: CRC Press.
- [8] Kibble, S. (1998). *Drugs and development in South Africa: How Europe could help*. London: Catholic Institute for International Relations, 32.
- [9] Blaauwberg Online. Available at: www.blaauwberg.net
- [10] Atkins, A. (1997). *The Illegal drugs trade and development in South Africa: Some observations*. London: Catholic Institute for International Relations.
- [11] *Substance Abuse Trends in South Africa: Implications* (1999). South African Medical Research Council (SAMR). Cape Town.
- [12] Oosthuysen, H.; Handley, A. (Ed.) (1998). *South Africa the global drug network. The illegal drug trade in Southern Africa: International dimensions to a local crisis*. Johannesburg: The South African Institute of International Affairs, 121–134.

- [13] Freud, S. (1885) *Uber Coca*. Verlag Press.
- [14] Legget, T. (2002). *Drugs and Crime in South Africa. A study in three cities*. ISS Monograph, No. 69.
- [15] Hess, K. M., Hess, C. H., Cho, H. L. (2018). *Introduction to Law Enforcement and Criminal Justice*. Boston: Cengage Learning.
- [16] National Institute of Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism. Available at: <https://www.niaaa.nih.gov/>
- [17] Yesufu, S. (2021). The socio-economic impact of the Covid-19: a South African perspective on its impact on the socio-economic, inequality, security, and food systems. *ScienceRise*, 4, 68–79. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2313-8416.2021.002036>
- [18] Mthembu, P. M., Mwenesongole, E. M., Cole, M. D. (2018). Chemical profiling of the street cocktail drug “nyaope” in South Africa using GC–MS I: Stability studies of components of “nyaope” in organic solvents. *Forensic Science International*, 292, 115–124. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2018.08.001>
- [19] Madiga, M. C., Mokwena, K. (2022). Depression Symptoms among Family Members of Nyaope Users in the City of Tshwane, South Africa. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19 (7), 4097. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19074097>
- [20] Smith, A. (2020) What is Nyaope (Whoonga)? What are the ingredients and effects of the drug cocktail on the body? Available at: www.buzzsouthafrica.com/nyaope
- [21] Medical News Today. Available at: <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com>
- [22] Web Medicine. Available at: <https://www.webmed.com/anabolicsteroids>
- [23] The Republic of South Africa Government Drug Master Plan 2013–2017. Available at: https://extranet.who.int/ncdccc/Data/ZAF_B10_National%20drug%20masterplan.pdf
- [24] The Drugs and Drugs Trafficking Act 140 of 1992, Republic of South Africa Government. Available at: https://www.gov.za/sites/default/files/gcis_document/201409/a1401992.pdf
- [25] National Liquor Act (2003). Available at: <https://www.gov.za/documents/liquor-act>
- [26] Education Laws Amendment Act. No. 31 (2007). Available at: http://www.saflii.org/za/legis/num_act/elaa2007235.pdf
- [27] National Road Traffic Act. No. 93 (1996). Available at: <https://www.gov.za/documents/national-road-traffic-act>
- [28] Sanca National. Available at: <https://www.sancanational.info>
- [29] Sabc News. Available at: <https://www.sabcnews.com>
- [30] SAnews. Available at: <https://www.sanews.gov.za>
- [31] The South African. Available at: <https://www.thesouthafrican.com>
- [32] Scope and the threat of organised crime in the SADC region. ISS Monograph. No. 60. (2001)
- [33] Irish, J., Qhobosheane, K. (2003). Penetrating state and business: Organised crime in South Africa. ISS Monograph.
- [34] Vesley, M. (2009). Africa highway to drug hell. *Africa Business*, 253.
- [35] Newman, G. (2002). Tackling Police corruption in South Africa: South Africa. Center for the Study of Violence and Reconciliation.